

Studies on the solution equilibria involved in some copper(II) and zinc(II) Schiff base complex systems

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Investigations on the equilibrium chemistry of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (A)-L-valine, L-phenylalanine and DL-tryptophane (B) systems show that in the M(AB), M(AB)A and M(AB)₂ type of complexes, the Schiff base(AB) binds in a terdentate manner.

Pyridine derivatives play important role in many biological reactions¹. 2-Pyridinecarboxaldehyde has been found to be involved in enzyme reactions². The derivatives of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde find extensive applications in medicine³. The Schiff base complexes of 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and its derivatives have been reported⁴ to possess high super oxide dismutase activities. In continuation of our investigations on the solution equilibria of transition metal ion-Schiff base complexes^{5,6}, the present paper reports Cu^{II}/Zn^{II}-2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde (pyal) (A)-L-valine (val), L-phenylalanine (phe) and DL-tryptophane (trp)(B) systems.

Results and Discussion

The Cu^{II}-Schiff base complex systems showed the presence of MAB and MA₂B type of complexes, while in the corresponding Zn^{II} systems in addition to these complexes MA₂B₂ has also been detected (Table 2). The binary complexes accounted during the computation of Schiff base complex equilibrium are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Stability constants for proton, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} binary complexes with pyal(A), val, phe and trp(B)

Temp. 25°, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³

Parameters	Cu ^{II}				Zn ^{II}			
	pyal ^a	val ^b	phe ^b	trp ^b	pyal ^a	val ^b	phe ^b	trp ^b
log β _{11A}	3.84	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
log β _{MA}	2.65	-	-	-	1.67	-	-	-
log β _{MA₂}	4.99	-	-	-	3.27	-	-	-
log β _{11B}	-	2.24	2.23	2.20	-	-	-	-
log β _{11₂B}	-	9.65	9.31	9.43	-	-	-	-
log β _{MB}	-	8.09	8.05	7.98	-	4.75	4.35	4.30
log β _{MB₂}	-	14.38	14.45	14.36	-	8.75	8.28	8.30

^aRef. 4, ^bRef. 11.

Table 2. Stability constants for the ternary complexes for M^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems

Metal ion	ligand (B)	log β _{MAB}	log β _{MA₂B}	log β _{MA₂B₂}
Cu ^{II}	val	16.86	19.41	-
	phe	16.71	19.25	-
	trp	16.62	19.42	-
Zn ^{II}	val	10.29	12.21	16.71
	phe	10.17	12.05	16.49
	trp	10.12	12.38	16.53

Stability and structure of MAB complexes : The log β_{MAB} values in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) and the corresponding Zn^{II} systems are 16.86, 16.71, 16.62 and 10.29, 10.17, 10.12, respectively. The schemes indicating the stepwise formation constants of the ternary complex systems show that the formation of ternary complex species are preferred compared to the binary complex formation. Such a scheme in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system is given below :

If the CuAB species is considered as a simple mixed ligand complex without inter-ligand interaction, then the theoretically calculated⁷ log β value for CuAB species would be ~9.99. But the experimental value is 16.86 log units, which indicates the presence of strong inter-ligand interaction between the CHO group of pyal and the amino group of val leading to the formation of terdentate Schiff base ligand (AB), binding the metal ion through the pyridine and imino nitrogens and the carboxylato oxygen atoms. The fusion of

two independent ligands to the multi-ring formation by the same ligand (AB) enhances the entropy and leads to the stability of the complex.

The $\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$ values of Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-phe and trp(B) systems are 16.71 and 16.62, respectively. These values are comparable to that of 16.86 in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system, indicating same type of binding in the CuAB species in all these three systems. This also shows that the phenyl group in the ligand and the indole group in the trp ligand exert negligible steric influence on the formation and stability of the ternary Schiff base complexes respectively in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-phe and trp(B) systems.

Similar to the CuAB species in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems, the ZnAB species in the Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems also exhibit higher stability (Table 2). If we consider them as simple mixed ligand complexes then the statistically calculated⁷ $\log \beta_{\text{ZnAB}}$ values are respectively 6.31, 6.08 and 6.09. But the respective higher experimentally found $\log \beta_{\text{ZnAB}}$ values of 10.29, 10.17 and 10.12 indicate that ZnAB species are also Schiff base complexes, where the terdentate Schiff base (AB) binds Zn^{II} through all the three available donors. Further, the comparable $\log \beta_{\text{ZnAB}}$ values in these three systems show that the phenyl group in phe and indole moiety in the trp ligands exert little steric influence on the formation of ZnAB Schiff base complexes.

The species distribution diagrams also point to the fact that the formation of the ternary Schiff base complex MAB is preferred over the formation of binary species. In the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems the CuAB species is predominantly present in the pH range 5.5–7.5 and its concentration reaches upto a maximum of ~70%, where the Cu^{II} : pyal is kept at 1 : 1 ratio. In the 1 : 2 systems, the CuAB is still more predominant reaching a maximum of ~80%. In the Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems, the ZnAB is the dominating species between pH 6.8 and 7.8 and it is found to be present to a maximum of 70% of the total metal ion in the 1 : 1 system and upto ~80% in the 1 : 2 systems.

The electronic absorption spectrum of the CuAB complex in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-val(B) system recorded at pH 6.38 in the 1 : 1 system shows a well defined broad absorption band at 656 nm. This corresponds to the *d-d* transition due to the square-planar environment of ligand field around Cu^{II} ion⁸. Thus a square-planar structure can be assigned to CuAB, where the three corners of the square are occupied by the three donor atoms of the Schiff base (AB) and the fourth corner is filled by a solvent water molecule.

Stability and structure of MA₂B complex : The $\log \beta$ values for the CuA₂B complex species in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-

val, phe and trp(B) systems are respectively, 19.41, 19.25 and 19.42. The calculated⁷ $\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2\text{B}}$ values if they are considered to be simple mixed ligand complexes⁷ are 12.48, 12.52 and 12.47 log units, respectively. The higher experimental values lead to the conclusion that the CuA₂B species is a Schiff base complex of the type Cu(AB)A. The Schiff base (AB) is coordinated to Cu^{II} tridentately and the second pyal is bound through its pyridine nitrogen alone. The $\log \beta$ value of CuA₂B complex in the Cu^{II}-pyal(A)-trp(B) system shows a difference. The stability constant value of 2.80 for the formation of Cu(AB)A from CuAB is higher than that for the formation of CuA₂ from CuA by 0.44 log units. This is not large enough to consider the additional coordination of the CHO group of the second pyal ligand. However, this enhancement of stability can be explained⁹ by considering the possible molecular recognition between the free aldehydic group of the second pyal and the NH group of the indole moiety present in the neighbouring complex species leading to intermolecular hydrogen bonding.

The $\log \beta$ values for the ZnA₂B complex species in the Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems, respectively are 12.21, 12.05 and 12.38, while the calculated⁷ values if they were simple mixed ligand complexes are 7.95, 7.71 and 7.72 log units, respectively. The higher experimental values clearly show that the ZnA₂B species are also Schiff base complexes of the type Zn(AB)A, where (AB) is coordinated to Zn^{II} in a terdentate mode and the second pyal binds through the pyridine nitrogen alone. Moreover, the higher stability of the Zn(AB)A species in the Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-trp(B) system can also be explained by the molecular recognition between the uncoordinated CHO group of the second pyal and the NH group in the indole moiety of the nearby complex.

The Cu(AB)A species have been found to be formed above pH 7.0 and reaches a maximum of ~35% of the total metal ion at pH 7.5. The Zn(AB)A complex is formed above pH 7.0 and accounts for a maximum of ~30% of the total Zn^{II} at pH 8.5.

Stability and structure of MA₂B₂ complex . Only in the Zn^{II}-pyal(A)-val, phe and trp(B) systems this type of species has been detected. The $\log \beta$ values obtained are respectively 16.71, 16.49 and 16.53. The respective statistically calculated⁷ $\log \beta$ values if they were simple mixed ligand complexes without inter-ligand interaction are 12.32, 11.85 and 11.87. The higher experimental values distinctly point to the fact that ZnA₂B₂ species are bis (Schiff base) complexes of the type Zn(AB)₂ where both the Schiff base ligands (AB) are bound in a terdentate mode leading to octahedral structure. Further, the

$\log \beta_{Zn(AB)_2}$ values (Table 2) in these systems are comparable to each other. This shows that the side-chain structure in the secondary amino acids does not exert any influence on the formation and stability of Schiff base complexes.

The $Zn(AB)_2$ species have been found to be formed only after pH 7.5 and there is an increase in its concentration after pH 8.0. In the 1 : 1 systems, the maximum concentration of $Zn(AB)_2$ species is only ~30% whereas in the 1 : 2 systems it is found to be present to about 50% of the total metal ion concentration.

Experimental

The metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade. The ligand pyal (pure grade Lancaster) was further purified by distilling under reduced pressure. The amino acids (puris, Fluka) were used as such. In the ternary Schiff base complex systems the equilibrium was attained slowly. Hence a batch-wise titration procedure was adopted^{5,6}. The details of the equipment used for the pH-titration method and electronic spectral measurements have been described earlier⁶. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and ionic

strength of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃). The calculations were done using the computer program¹⁰ on a Wipro computer with Pentium.

References

1. R. K. Murray and D. K. Granner. "Harper's Biochemistry", Appleton and Lange, Stamford, 1996.
2. M. Hughes and R. H. Prince, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, **40**, 707
3. P. Eyer and W. Hell, *Arch. Pharm (Weinheim)*, 1986, **319**, 558.
4. C. M. Liu, R. G. Xiong and K. K. Cheung, *Polyhedron*, 1996, **15**, 4565.
5. M. S. Nair, S. T. David and M. Anbu, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 823.
6. M. S. Nair and S. T. David, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 472.
7. H. Siegel in "IUPAC Coordination Chemistry 20", ed. D. Banerjee, Pergamon, Oxford, 1980.
8. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1971.
9. M. T. B. Luiz, B. Szpoganicz and A. E. Martel, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1997, **254**, 345.
10. D. L. Leussing and D. Hopgood, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **32**, 505.
11. A. E. Martel and R. M. Smith, "Critical Stability Constants", Vols. 1-6, 1974-1989.